

EFFECT OF MOBILE MONEY SERVICES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF MICRO-BUSINESSES IN BIDA, NIGER STATE.

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of mobile money services on the performance of micro-businesses in Bida, Niger State, Nigeria. Mobile money, which is described as an online financial service, through which a transaction is made possible using a mobile phone and without the necessity of having a formal bank account, has become an aspect of financial inclusion within the developing economies. The study relies on primary data of 383 micro-business proprietors who were picked by using stratified random sampling. Analytical software such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multivariate regression (MVREG) was used to test the assumed relationship between mobile money adoption and performance indicators, proxied revenue growth and profitability. Findings indicates that the use of mobile money ($= 0.121, p < 0.01$) and profitability ($= 0.109, p < 0.01$) has a significant positive effect on cash flow, transaction costs, customer convenience, and, as a result, profitability. The results are consistent with the world literature that highlights the transformative nature of digital finance in reducing the financial inclusion gap. The study recommends that enhancing agent networks of mobile money, enhancing digital infrastructure, and enhancing financial literacy can help to enhance micro-business resilience and spur inclusive local economic development.

Keywords: Mobile money, Micro-businesses, Financial inclusion, Revenue growth, Profitability.

1. Background to the study

Micro-businesses have continued to play a significant role in the socio-economic growth and development of Nigeria because it plays a significant role in the creation

of employment, household income and local production. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2022) indicates that in Nigeria, micro, small, and medium-sized businesses (MSMEs) comprise 96 percent of the business and employs approximately 84 percent of the labour force. Micro-businesses are limited by poor access to finance, low capital accumulation, and high transaction costs despite their significance (Abiola & Moses, 2021).

Irrespective of their socio-economic significance, micro-businesses are continued to be limited especially in the sphere of access to the finance. Conventional financial intermediaries, sometimes located in cities, have very strict collateralization, high transaction fees, and bureaucratic lending mechanisms that lock most of the informal entrepreneurs out (Owolabi & Lawson, 2023). Consequently, informal networks of credit, rotating savings or personal funds, which are not always sufficient, irregular, and unsustainable, often become the only options available to many micro-business owners (Eneji et al., 2020). To fill this financing gap, alternative mechanisms of improving financial inclusion have come up; these are digital financial services (DFS). Among them, mobile money services that enable people and businesses to deposit and transfer funds and withdraw and pay bills through mobile phones are outstanding due to the potential to reach the unbanked. Mobile money services eliminate formal bank accounts, lower transaction costs, and offer convenient, real-time, financial solutions (Aker & Mbiti, 2010; Jack & Suri, 2014). Digital transformation in the delivery of financial services in Nigeria is depicted by the emergence of platforms like Paga, OPay, PalmPay, and FirstMonie.

Nevertheless, the mobile money promise is not completely actualized in places like Bida, Niger State. Micro-businesses still have adoption and adoption barriers that inhibit adoption and impact even though agent networks exist. These are low level of digital literacy, lack of network connectivity, no proper awareness, and lack of trust towards digital platform. Besides, as mobile money should streamline operations, minimise money-handling risks, and increase customer coverage, there is limited empirical evidence in Nigeria on the direct impact of mobile money on the performance indicators of micro-business (e.g. revenue growth and profitability). The majority of the current literature has considered mobile money and financial inclusion on household level or commercial bank profitability, but with little consideration to the micro-enterprises themselves (Nwachukwu et al., 2019; Oyetoyan et al., 2021).

The research gap leaves the following questions: How far can the adoption of mobile money lead to measurable increases in the performance of micro-businesses in local settings like Bida? Will the use of mobile money improve the growth of revenues and profitability or is the potential hampered by high transaction fees and lack of reliability in services? The answers to these questions are very important not only in the academic research but also in policy interventions that can be applied to reinforce the financial inclusion strategy in Nigeria. Thus, the aim of this paper is to investigate how mobile money services impact the performance of the micro business in Bida,

Niger State, in relation to revenue growth and profitability. The study helps to address the existing gap in knowledge and offer evidence-based information to inform policymakers, financial institutions, and micro-entrepreneurs by placing the analysis within the context of the larger discourse on financial inclusion and digital transformation.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review of Mobile Money and Business Performance

Mobile money is a digital financial system that allows individuals to complete financial transactions with the use of a mobile phone without necessarily having formal bank accounts (Aker & Mbiti, 2010). Through a system of mobile agents, it makes deposits, withdrawals, money transfer, payment of bills and savings. Its distinguishing characteristics are its accessibility, affordability, and immediacy of the transactions, which make it especially applicable to the low-income populations and micro-enterprises that trade with the use of cash in their economies (Webb, 2024).

Mobile money has its own benefits in the case of micro-businesses. It eliminates the use of cash handling, and thus, minimises the risk of theft and delays in transactions. It also increases the efficiency in operation because it helps in paying the suppliers on time, makes sales remotely and makes the customers convenient. Moreover, mobile money facilitates improved liquidity management, in which the earnings made by the entrepreneurs can be deposited every day and credit can be provided based on transaction history. In that regard, business performance is gauged using sales growth, profitability, customer reach, and sustainability (Delmar et al., 2003).

Nevertheless, the advantages of mobile money implementation are not self-evident. Such aspects as digital literacy, network stability, transaction fees, and confidence in the digital environment also determine the degree to which micro-businesses will be able to use mobile money to enhance performance (EFInA, 2023). Therefore, the correlation between mobile money and micro-business performance is still relative to context and firm specific factors.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Three closely associated theoretical perspectives can be used to explain the relationship between mobile money adoption and micro-business performance:

I. **Resource-based View (RBV):** This perspective, firstly, came up with Penrose (1959) and has been developed by Barney (1991), suggests that firms have sustained competitive advantage because of resources which are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable. Mobile money is a strategic intangible resource in the micro-businesses. It improves liquidity, lowers transaction costs, and improves access to markets that competitors may not always be able to recreate because they do not have access to such digital tools. By way of example, daily deposit and mobile payment minimises security risk and enables micro-businesses to reinvest their earnings in time thus consolidating competitive advantage.

ii. **Technology Acceptance Model (TAM):** Davis (1989) came up with TAM to describe how users adopt technologies with less focus on intention to use as a determinant of behavioural intention and the focus on perceived usefulness and ease of use as the determinants of intention to use. Perceived usefulness is associated with how the mobile money will help them to conduct transactions faster, better cash flow, and more convenient to the customers in the case of micro-businesses in Bida. Perceived ease of use is associated with the ease with which micro-entrepreneurs believe that mobile apps or POS interface can be easily used. According to empirical studies on Ghana (Serwaah, 2023), the perceptions in question have a direct influence on SME adoption decisions and the business performance thereof.

iii. **Financial Intermediation Theory:** According to Gurley and Shaw (1960), financial intermediaries minimise the transactions costs and information asymmetry, which enhance capital allocation. The mobile money agents, who are decentralised intermediaries, bring financial services to the hitherto excluded groups. They support the micro-enterprise safe savings, small scale credit and the real time transfer of funds to micro-enterprises. This is consistent with the results of Kenya (Jack and Suri, 2014), where M-Pesa made it easy to manage the liquidity and boost the resilience of small enterprises.

The combination of these theories implies that the adoption of mobile money can reinforce the performance of micro-businesses through the strategic resources (RBV) by facilitating the adoption of technology (TAM), and broadening the financial intermediation in resource-strained setting.

2.3 Empirical Review

There is empirical evidence of this transformative role of mobile money in improving the outcome of micro and small enterprises in the global and African experience. Khan and Shahid (2024) found in South Asia that the use of mobile payment had a positive effect on perceived business success and subjective well-being, particularly in women. This can be related to RBV, since mobile money presented a competitive resource, which was gender sensitive, whereby women entrepreneurs could overcome the resource limitation.

On the African lens Ghana, Serwaah (2023) discovered that performance expectancy and effort expectancy forecasted the adoption of mobile money in SME, which increased profitability. On the same note, Nyello (2018) demonstrated that mobile money transactions in Tanzania had a positive impact on improving sales revenue and lowering costs, but not without entrepreneurial orientation. This brings out the resource heterogeneity argument of RBV: the returns are different based on the capability of the entrepreneurs to use mobile money to their advantage.

Fabregas & Yokossi (2022) carried out a quasi experimental study, in Kenya, which further supported the idea that increasing the number of mobile money agents increased the local economic activity, by using the amount of night time light as a measure of local economic activity. Their results are an example of the Financial

Intermediation Theory since it demonstrated that there was a direct correlation between the geographic reach of mobile money and economic life.

Jack & Suri (2014) illustrated a similar effect in Kenya where M-Pesa had a positive impact on household welfare and entrepreneurship by reducing the cost of transactions and increasing risk sharing. Their article is empirical evidence of the Financial Intermediation Theory in that mobile money successfully addressed the gap between borrowers and savers. Equally, Wanyonyi (2021) established that in microenterprises operating on mobile money, the growth of sales and stability of revenues were higher, which confirms the projection of TAM that the perceived usefulness impacts the adoption and the consequences.

Nigeria is increasing its evidence although in a disjointed manner. Oyetoyan *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that the use of mobile money enhanced the performance of small and medium enterprises, but the use of this type of money was curtailed because of cyber-security issues. Nwachukwu *et al.* (2019) emphasised the weak yet positive correlation of mobile money services and financial inclusion due to the high transaction expenses and digital illiteracy. Intensively closer to Bida, Ibrahim & Salihu (2022) discovered that the adoption of mobile money minimised transaction delays and improved the record-keeping of traders in the area, which leads to the RBV argument that digital finance offers micro-businesses with unique operational resources.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research design in this study involved descriptive survey research design, which is suitable in research that captures cross-sectional data on the use of mobile money services and how it impacts performance of micro-businesses. The design allows collecting quantitative information about many respondents and subsequently provides statistical analysis and hypothesis testing without manipulation of the variables in the study.

3.2 Population and Sampling

The population sample was the owners of micro-businesses in the city of Bida Metropolis in Nigeria. Such businesses were selectively invited due to the fact that they pilfer the informal economy and are often involved in cash dealings. The minimum sample size was calculated through the Cochran (1963) formula that was used to calculate the size of an infinite population with a level of confidence of 95 percent and a margin of error of 5 percent and gave a minimum of 384 respondents. In order to cover the non-response, 400 questionnaires were conducted. And of these, 383 of the valid responses were collected, which was equivalent to a response rate of 95.7 percent, and adequate to give the analysis sufficient power to conduct regression.

A purposive and quota sampling method was used. Micro-businesses were selected purposely based on relevance (active transactional based enterprises) and quotas

ensured proportional representation among the major sectors of the micro-business such as food vending, tailoring, petty trading, and services. This strategy gave sufficient diversification in the type of business, the nature of the owner, and financial practises.

3.3 Data Collection Instrument

A structured questionnaire was used to gather primary information whereby the questionnaire was categorised into different sections such as socio-demographic factors, adoption of mobile money services, and business performance measures (revenue growth and profitability). The tool used both closed-ended Likert-scale questions and categorical answers, which allowed a descriptive and inferential analysis.

3.4 Model Specification

In an attempt to research the impact of mobile money adoption on business performance, the research indicated a multivariate regression (MVREG) model, which can be used to concurrently estimate the determinants of increased revenue and profitability. The model is expressed as:

$$RG_i = \beta_0(1) + \beta_1(1)MMS_i + \beta_2(1)X_i + u_i(1)$$

$$PF_i = \beta_0(2) + \beta_1(2)MMS_i + \beta_2(2)X_i + u_i(2)$$

where:

RG_i revenue growth of firm i

PF_i profitability of firm i

MMS_i mobile money service usage (frequency, volume, diversity of transactions)

X_i vector of control variables (firm size, owner's education, financial literacy, age, gender, sector, etc.)

u_i error terms, potentially correlated across equations.

This system allows testing whether mobile money adoption significantly influences both revenue growth and profitability while controlling for firm and owner characteristics.

3.5 Data Analysis

The data collected were coded and analysed with the help of Stata version 16 that is used in the social science research because it can work with large quantities of data and can implement multivariate models (StataCorp, 2019). The study was done using a set of analytical methods. Descriptive statistics that involve frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations were determined to describe the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and summarise the distribution of major study variables. The descriptive analysis lays a necessary background of the data organisation and preconditions the further inferential analysis (Field, 2018).

The correlation analysis was performed to investigate the strength and direction of the associations between the adoption of mobile money and micro-business performance indicators (revenue growth and profitability). Before the modelling of linear relationships, correlation is a suitable initial measure of the identification of

relationships (Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

The researcher used a multivariate regression (MVREG) model to concurrently estimate the impact of mobile money usage on the growth of revenue and profitability. MVREG method is effective as it considers potential contemporaneous correlation among the errors of the two performance equations and hence the parameter estimates have an enhanced estimate compared to those of one equation OLS models (Greene, 2012).

Lastly, diagnostic tests were performed in order to guarantee the strength of the model results. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was calculated to help test the presence of multicollinearity between the explanatory variables; none of the VIF values amounted to the standard high level of multicollinearity of 10 (Hair et al., 2019). The heteroskedasticity was identified using Breusch Pagan test and the findings indicated that there was nothing like homoscedasticity in the error variances. Moreover, the presence of the specification error was also rejected using the Ramsey RESET test, which means that the model was specified correctly (Wooldridge, 2016). In totality, these diagnostic tests confirmed the suitability of the regression models and enhanced faith in the empirical results.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Total Respondents
Gender	Female	111	28.98	383
	Male	272	71.02	383
Marital Status	Unmarried	116	30.29	383
	Married	267	69.71	383

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

Table 1 shows gender and marital status distribution of the respondents. A total of 383 out of the 383 sampled micro business owners (272 or 71.02 male 111 or 28.98 female) were sampled, which means that there was a high concentration of male ownership in the sampled population. This finding aligns with the findings of other previous studies that indicate that men are more likely to own and operate businesses in the developing economies and this is mainly because of the gendered differences in the access to capital, markets networks and available entrepreneurial training (Klapper & Parker, 2011; Minniti & Naudé, 2010). This relatively small percentage of female-owned enterprises could be evidence of structural constraints like a lack of access to formal finance, socio-cultural restrictions and conflicting household roles that prevent women to engage in entrepreneurial activities (World Bank, 2020).

In terms of marital status, the findings indicate that 267 (69.71) of the respondents were married as opposed to 116 (30.29) revealing that the respondents were not married. This is an indication that most owners of the enterprises in Bida are married

people. Academically, the marital status has been attributed to entrepreneurial decision making and performance. Entrepreneurs who are married have the benefit of being more socially and financially stable, enjoying stronger social networks, and there is a possibility of having access to pooled household resources and this can have a positive impact on business survival and growth (Collins et al., 2011; Jennings and McDougald, 2007). Furthermore, marriage and inclusion of more relatives can lead to easy access to credit, clients and business ventures (Danes et al., 2009).

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics on Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Age	44.28	10.53	20	75	-0.04	2.53
Gender	0.71	0.45	0	1	-0.93	1.86
Marital Status	0.70	0.46	0	1	-0.86	1.74
Mobile Money Usage	7.83	4.55	0	15	-0.16	1.81
Revenue Growth	3.19	0.73	1	5	-0.15	2.63
Profitability	3.24	0.72	1	5	-0.15	2.80
Firm Size	15.42	8.53	1	30	-0.10	1.83
Owner' Education Years	10.44	5.87	0	20	-0.10	1.89
Financial Literacy Score	50.48	28.36	0.09	98.47	-0.03	1.84

Source: Authors Computation, 2025.

Table 4.2 displays the descriptive statistics of the study variables, the measures of central tendency, the dispersion and the distribution shape. The mean age of the respondents was 44.28 years (SD =10.53) and the age span was 20-75. This means that the majority of enterprise owners in Bida are in the middle to late adulthood, which is a stage that is generally related with accrued experience, enhanced ability to mobilise resources, and a relative aversion to risk, all of which determines the decisions of the entrepreneur (Lévesque & Minniti, 2006).

The variable of gender (mean = 0.71, SD = 0.45) indicates that there were about 71 percent males among the respondents. The skewness is negative (-0.93), which indicates that the distribution is tilted towards men, as it has been previously revealed that there are gender differences in the ownership of enterprises in developing economies (Klapper and Parker, 2011). On the same note, the variable of marital status (mean = 0.70, SD = 0.46) indicates that approximately 70 percent of the respondents were married. It agrees with the literature that marital stability is associated with business ownership in terms of pooled household resources, social support, and network of spouses, which contribute to improved access to capital and markets (Jennings & McDougald, 2007; Danes et al., 2009).

Regarding digital financial practises, the average score of mobile money usage was 7.83 or 15 (SD = 4.55) indicating moderate use of mobile money by micro-businesses. The fact that the skewness is almost symmetrical (-0.16) means that low and high rates of engagement with mobile money were prevalent in the sample.

With regards to business results, the average score in terms of growth in revenue was

3.19 (SD = 0.73) and the average score in terms of profitability was 3.24 (SD = 0.72) on a five-point scale. These values imply that, averagely, the respondents viewed their enterprises as average performers. The distributions were more or less normal (skewness = -0.15), which was favourable to their application in multivariate regression analysis (Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

The sample can also be further contextualised by other enterprise characteristics. The mean size of the firm was 15.42 (SD = 8.53) indicating the micro to small scale-sized businesses. The mean years of education of owners were 10.44 (SD = 5.87) which implies that the majority of them had secondary school education, which is closely linked with the use of financial technologies (Ayyagari et al., 2011). The financial literacy score was 50.48 out of 100 (SD = 28.36), and heterogeneity was not found as the highest and lowest scores ranged between 0.09 and 98.47, respectively, (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014).

The values of skewness and kurtosis of the majority of variables are acceptable (-1 to +1 skewness, close to 3 kurtosis), indicating approximate normality. This makes the dataset more suitable to make inferences using regression since the assumption of linearity and normal distribution of residuals appears to be fulfilled rather well (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis

Variables	AGE	GEN	MS	MMS	RG	PROF	FS	OEY	FLS
AGE	1.00								
GEN	0.004	1.00							
MS	-0.02	0.005	1.00						
MMS	-0.01	0.02	0.05	1.00					
RG	0.07	0.02	0.08	0.73	1.00				
PROF	0.07	0.01	0.10	0.67	0.92	1.00			
FS	0.02	-0.01	0.04	-0.04	-0.06	-0.05	1.00		
OEY	0.01	0.07	0.04	-0.05	-0.04	0.001	0.04	1.00	
FLS	-0.03	0.04	-0.03	-0.07	-0.08	-0.03	-0.02	-0.04	1.00

Source: Authors Computation

The table 4.3 shows the correlation coefficient of the study variables, the demographic variables, the mobile money usage and the business performance indicators. The results indicate extremely high positive relationship among revenue growth (RG), profitability (PROF) ($r = 0.92$) that is expected as well as in line with what is already known in the literature (Delmar et al., 2003; Davidsson et al., 2009). This is an indication that, the higher the growth in sales recorded by firms, the better are the chances of improved profitability due to the interrelationship that exists between the two dimensions of performance.

In a similar manner, the utilisation of the mobile money (MMS) has a strong and positive relationship with the increase in revenues ($r = 0.73$) as well as the profitability ($r = 0.67$). This gives initial support on the fact that enterprises that make active use of mobile money services are likely to report improved performance

outcomes. These results are consistent with other recent studies in Sub-Saharan Africa that state that digital financial services enhance the efficiency of transactions, lower costs, and increase customer bases, leading to the growth and profitability of a firm (Jack & Suri, 2014; Serwaah, 2023).

Interestingly, demographic variables including age ($r = -0.01$), gender ($r = 0.02$), marital status ($r = 0.05$) and years of education of the owner (OEY, $r = -0.05$) had weak and statistically insignificant correlations with MMS. This implies the possibility of quite widespread adoption of mobile money services in Bida within socio-demographic groups, but not limited to certain age, gender, or education groups. This is contrary to the results in other settings, as younger, more educated, or male businesspeople tend to use digital finance more often (Aker & Mbiti, 2010; Oyetoyan et al., 2021). The identified trend could be associated with the mainstream of using mobile money in the Nigerian business setting caused by its perceived convenience and the need in the economies with the cash character.

The correlation between the size of firms (FS) and the performance indicators (RG, $r = -0.06$; PROF, $r = -0.05$) were also negative and insignificant, which means that bigger enterprises in the sample did not always have a higher growth or profitability than smaller firms had. This fact is relevant to the discussion that the performance of firms in microenterprise-based settings is not as much scale-driven but more resource-consumption and availability to financial technologies-driven (Beck & Demirguc-Kunt, 2006).

Lastly, financial literacy score (FLS) had weak and negative correlations with revenue growth ($r = -0.08$) as well as profitability ($r = -0.03$). Although this is paradoxical, this could indicate that even the respondents who were financially literate did not always get better results, which may be caused by the structural factors like unfavourable market conditions, inadequate access to the formal credit, or infrastructural limitations. Indicative paradoxical results were also noted in Nigeria, where financial literacy does not necessarily mean the enterprise profitability due to institutional and contextual constraints (Ogunleye et al., 2020).

4.2 Regression Results

Table 4.4: *Multivariate Regression on effect of Mobile Money Services on Micro-business Performance*

Dependent Variables:	Revenue Growth	Profitability
Independent Variables		
<i>Age</i>	0.005*** (0.002)	0.004** (0.002)
<i>Gender</i>	0.042 (0.050)	0.007 (0.052)
<i>Marital Status</i>	0.034 (0.050)	0.048 (0.052)
<i>Mobile Money Service</i>	0.121*** (0.005)	0.109*** (0.005)
<i>Firm Size</i>	-0.004 (0.003)	-0.004 (0.003)
<i>Owner's Education Years</i>	0.003 (0.004)	0.008 (0.004)
<i>Financial Literacy Score</i>	-0.001 (0.001)	0.001 (0.001)
<i>F-stat</i>	68.43 (0.0000)	56.31 (0.0000)
<i>R-Squared</i>	0.6478	0.6022
<i>N</i>	383	383

Notes: Robust standard errors are in parentheses, P values: significance *10%; **5%; ***1%.

Source: Computed by the researcher (extracted from Stata 14)

Table 4.4 shows the outcome of the multivariate regression (MVREG) analysis on the impact of mobile money on performance of micro-businesses whereby the growth of revenue and profitability are the dependent variables. The findings reveal that the age of the enterprise owner is significantly and positively related to both the revenue growth (0.005, $p < 0.01$) and the profitability (0.004, $p < 0.05$). This implies the attraction of older entrepreneurs to greater performance in business, which may be explained by the advanced experience in management, good social network, and gained knowledge in the market. The result is in line with previous research claiming that age-related experience has a positive predictive of entrepreneurial performance, but to a certain extent (Lévesque & Minniti, 2006; Kautonen et al., 2014).

On the other hand, the gender and marital status did not indicate a statistically significant predictor of the two performance measures. Despite the fact that the overwhelming majority of the sample population was men, the regression outcomes show that there is no correlation between the performance of a business and gender and marital status once the other factors have been adjusted. This is in line with recent findings that structural variables like access to finance and the institutional environment can be important rather than demographic variables in the formation of firm performance (Minniti & Naudé, 2010).

The most remarkable discovery is that the impact of mobile money service usage (MMS) on the growth of revenues (= 0.121, $p < 0.01$) and profitability (= 0.109, $p < 0.01$) is very significant and positive. And this is where the main importance of

digital financial tools lies in boosting the efficiency of operations carried out by micro-businesses. Mobile money offers micro-entrepreneurs with a very important leverage to boost sales and enhance profit margins through the reduction of transaction costs, the expansion of customer bases, and the promotion of faster cash flows (Jack & Suri, 2014; Serwaah, 2023). This robust finding supports the theoretical assumption of the study and proves that mobile money is a radical impetus to micro-business performance in resource-bound settings.

Other variables including the size of the firm, the years of education of the owner, and financial literacy score did not have significant impacts. Firm size was not important, but had weak negative relationship, implying the possibility that the growth and profitability of micro-enterprises in Bida does not expand at the same rate in terms of employee size, which is also supported by the observation of Beck and Demirgües-kunt (2006) that small firms do not experience proportionate expansion. Financial literacy and education, which are usually linked to the improvement of decision-making, did not lead to quantifiable performance advantages. This can be a structural limitation in access to credit or a poor institutional environment that restricts the power of knowledge and skills to generate financial gains (Ogunleye et al., 2020).

The revenue growth model has a high overall model fit with an F-statistic of 68.43 ($p < 0.000$) and $R^2 = 0.6478$, and the profitability model has an F-statistic of 56.31 ($p < 0.000$) and $R^2 = 0.6022$. These values demonstrate that about 60-65 percent of the variation in business performance can be explained with the help of the explanatory variables, which shows the strength of the models.

4.3 Diagnostic Test

Table 4.5: *Diagnostic Test on effect of Mobile Money Services on Micro-business Performance*

Test Statistics	Assumptions	Revenue Growth	Profitability	Remark
<i>Multicollinearity</i>	VIF	1.03	1.03	Absence
<i>Breusch-Pagan</i>	Heteroskedasticity	0.2061	0.5155	Insignificant
<i>Ramsey RESET</i>	F-Statistic	0.5500	0.3448	Insignificant

Source: Author's Computation Extract from Stata (2025). Note, VIF is Variance Inflation Factor.

The Residual diagnostic test of the classical assumption of the estimation technique (model) is presented in Table 4.7 above and shows that the average VIF of both models (revenue growth and profitability) individually is 1.03 indicating a very low degree of correlation between predictors as this is lower than the generally accepted cut-off of 10 and a more stringent cut-off of 5 (O'Brien, 2007). This enhances the precision and explicability of the regression coefficients of the two models.

The Breusch-Pagan test of Heteroskedasticity of revenue growth model gave chi-square value of 1.60 and a p-value of 0.2061 and the profitability model gave chi-square value of 0.42 and p-value of 0.5155. Given that the p-value exceeds the

standard 5% level of significance, we do not disrespect the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity (Breusch and Pagan, 1979). This has shown that the variance of the residuals remains unchanged when the fitted values are varied and therefore the model is not heteroskedastic, thus fulfilling one of the Gauss Markov assumptions of OLS.

Likewise, Ramsey RESET test of Omitted Variable Bias showed F-statistic of 0.70, p-value of 0.5500 on revenue growth model, and F-statistic of 1.11, p-value of 0.3448 on profitability model. Considering our p-value, we do not reject the null hypothesis that the model does not exclude any variables (Ramsey, 1969). This implies that the functional form is specified correctly and that it has not omitted any major explanatory variables in the model.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper has analysed how mobile money has impacted performance of micro-businesses in Bida, Niger State. The findings based on the analysis of the data of 383 micro-enterprises using multivariate regression analysis have strong evidence that mobile money adoption has a significant positive impact on revenue growth and profitability. This finding points to the revolutionary nature of digital financial inclusion in resource-constrained environments, in which the classic banking system is frequently scarce.

Demographic variables such as gender, marital status and education were also not important predictors of business performance, indicating that digital financial tools are not limited by socio-demographic boundaries in promoting business development. Although the age of the owner had a positive and significant correlation with the performance, which portrays the usefulness of entrepreneurial experience, the firm size and financial literacy variables did not have statistically significant results. These results draw on the fact that translation of human capital benefits into quantifiable financial returns may be constrained by structural issues and institutional bottlenecks.

Therefore, the research advises that;

- i. **Marketing Mobile Money Ecosystems:** Policymakers need to further promote mobile money infiltration through fintech development, empowering agent systems, and affordable cost of transactions. This will make it easier to adopt it and be able to further boost the performance of businesses amongst micro-entrepreneurs.
- ii. **Mobile Money as an Element of MSME Development Policies:** Development agencies and governmental programmes focused on promoting micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are recommended to integrate the use of mobile money as the primary element of capacity building and support of financial programmes.
- iii. **Fix Institutional and Infrastructural Constraints:** Although financial literacy and education, in a vacuum, did not have a significant impact on performance, their potential value could be limited by poor institutional

- structures. The attention should hence be paid to enhancing access to credit, reliable electricity, and robust regulatory frameworks so that digital finance could prosper.
- iv. Support Inclusive Digital Finance: It is worthy to emphasise on lowering the hurdles among women entrepreneurs, who have been underrepresented in the ownership of businesses. Gender-sensitive policies, e.g. credit schemes targeting women, training on digital literacy, and customised mobile financial products can be used to close the gaps that exist.
 - v. Further the Collaboration of the Private Sector: Collaboration between mobile network operations and financial institutions and government agencies can fast track the innovation of mobile money products that will satisfy the varying needs of micro-business, especially in the rural and semi-urban locales.

References

- Abiola, J., & Moses, O. (2021). Financial inclusion and performance of micro and small enterprises in Nigeria. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 9(1), 45–57.
- Aker, J. C., & Mbiti, I. (2010). Mobile phones and economic development in Africa. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 24(3), 207–232.
- Ayyagari, M., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Maksimovic, V. (2011). Small vs. young firms across the world: Contribution to employment, job creation, and growth. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper 5631.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- Beck, T., & Demirgüç-Kunt, A. (2006). Small and medium-size enterprises: Access to finance as a growth constraint. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 30(11), 2931–2943.
- Cochran, W. G. (1963). *Sampling techniques* (2nd ed.). New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage.

- Danes, S. M., Lee, J., Stafford, K., & Heck, R. K. Z. (2009). The effects of ethnicity, families, and culture on entrepreneurial experience: An extension of sustainable family business theory. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 14(03), 229–268.
- Davidsson, P., Steffens, P., & Fitzsimmons, J. (2009). Growing profitable or growing from profits: Putting the horse in front of the cart. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 24(4), 388–406.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340.
- Delmar, F., Davidsson, P., & Gartner, W. B. (2003). Arriving at the high-growth firm. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 18(2), 189–216.
- EFInA. (2023). *Access to financial services in Nigeria 2023 survey*. Enhancing Financial Innovation & Access (EFInA).
- Eneji, M. A., John, S., & Adams, J. (2020). Informal credit markets and microenterprise financing in Nigeria. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 27(1), 45–64.
- Fabregas, R., & Yokossi, T. (2022). Mobile money, local economic activity, and development. *World Development*, 151, 105758.
- Field, A. (2018). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Greene, W. H. (2012). *Econometric analysis* (7th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Gujarati, D. N., & Porter, D. C. (2009). *Basic econometrics* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Gurley, J. G., & Shaw, E. S. (1960). *Money in a theory of finance*. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2019). *Multivariate data analysis* (8th ed.). Cengage.
- Ibrahim, I., & Salihu, M. (2022). Financial inclusion and digital transactions among traders in Niger State. *Nigerian Journal of Development Studies*, 5(2), 88–104.
- Jack, W., & Suri, T. (2014). Risk sharing and transactions costs: Evidence from Kenya's mobile money revolution. *American Economic Review*, 104(1), 183–223.
- Jennings, J. E., & McDougald, M. S. (2007). Work–family interface experiences and coping strategies: Implications for entrepreneurship research and practice. *Academy of Management Review*, 32(3), 747–760.
- Kautonen, T., Down, S., & Minniti, M. (2014). Ageing and entrepreneurial preferences. *Small Business Economics*, 42(3), 579–594.
- Khan, S., & Shahid, A. (2024). Mobile payments, entrepreneurial success and subjective wellbeing among micro-entrepreneurs. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 31(2), 205–224.
- Klapper, L., & Parker, S. (2011). Gender and the business environment for new firm creation. *World Bank Research Observer*, 26(2), 237–257.
- Lévesque, M., & Minniti, M. (2006). The effect of aging on entrepreneurial behavior.

- Journal of Business Venturing, 21(2), 177–194.
- Lusardi, A., & Mitchell, O. S. (2014). The economic importance of financial literacy: Theory and evidence. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 52(1), 5–44
- Minniti, M., & Naudé, W. (2010). What do we know about the patterns and determinants of female entrepreneurship across countries? *European Journal of Development Research*, 22(3), 277–293.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2022). *Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) survey report*. Abuja: NBS.
- Nwachukwu, T., Okoye, L., & Eze, S. (2019). Mobile money services and financial inclusion in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 9(1), 179–186.
- Nyello, R. (2018). Mobile money services and microenterprise growth in Tanzania. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 25(2), 101–120.
- Ogunleye, E. O., Adepoju, A. O., & Fagbemi, F. (2020). Financial literacy and small business performance in Nigeria: Do institutional factors matter? *Journal of African Business*, 21(4), 472–490.
- Owolabi, O., & Lawson, A. (2023). Credit constraints and informal sector financing in Nigeria: Implications for MSME growth. *Journal of Development Finance*, 7(1), 55–70.
- Oyetoyan, T. D., Lawal, I. A., & Alabi, J. O. (2021). Mobile money adoption and SME performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 9(2), 1–12.
- Penrose, E. (1959). *The theory of the growth of the firm*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Serwaah, E. (2023). Mobile money adoption and SME performance in Ghana. *African Journal of Business Research*, 14(3), 120–138.
- StataCorp. (2019). *Stata Statistical Software: Release 16*. College Station, TX: StataCorp LLC.
- Wanyonyi, M. (2021). Mobile money transfer services and microenterprise performance in Kenya. *Journal of African Business*, 22(4), 567–583.
- Waris, A., Nazir, M., Khan, A., Ali, H., & Gorski, M. (2024). E-banking and SME performance in developing economies. *Journal of Financial Services Research*, 48(2), 215–236.
- Webb, J. (2024). Mobile money and the digital economy: Opportunities for inclusive growth in Africa. *Journal of Financial Innovation*, 12(1), 45–62.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2016). *Introductory econometrics: A modern approach* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.